

SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-ARYLALKYL KETONES. PART I.

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The condensation product of *o*-methoxy-arylalkyl ketones with α -halogenated fatty esters is dehydrated yielding the unsaturated ester which easily forms coumarin derivatives either with sulphuric acid or hydriodic acid. The syntheses of 3-methyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin and 3:7-dimethyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin by the condensation of ethyl α -bromopropionate with 2-methoxy-5-chlorophenylethyl ketone and 2-methoxy-5-chloro-4-methylphenylethyl ketone respectively have been described.

In course of the synthetical studies on coumarins and chromones, 4-ethylcoumarins were formed and it was thought advisable to synthesise authentic 4-ethylcoumarins by unambiguous methods. *o*-Hydroxy-arylalkyl ketones, which are readily available either by Hoesch's reaction or by Fries' rearrangement of acylated phenols, may readily be converted to coumarin derivatives in the following way :—

(where R = H or an alkyl group).

The hydroxy-ester (I) is contaminated with the unsaturated ester (II) and hence the hydroxy-ester is always dehydrated with thionyl

chloride in the presence of pyridine. The ring-closure of (II) to (III) may be effected by heating with hydriodic acid (*d* 1'7) or by keeping overnight with cold concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1'84). In both cases the yield of the coumarin is almost quantitative.

The *o*-hydroxy-arylalkyl ketones have been used by Kostanecki and later on by Robinson for the synthesis of chromone derivatives. Heilbron and co-workers have found that coumarins are also formed by the action of the *o*-hydroxy-arylalkyl ketones with acid anhydrides in the presence of the sodium salt of the acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1263; 1934, 1311, 1581; 1936, 296; *cf.* Chakravarti and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 689). Stoermer and Friderici (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 324) and Mitter and Paul (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 271) submitted *o*-methoxybenzophenones to Reformatsky's reaction but the yields of the coumarins obtained were extremely poor.

This paper describes the synthesis of 3-methyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin and 3:7-dimethyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin from ethyl α -bromopropionate and the methoxy derivatives of the *o*-hydroxypropionophenones, obtained by Fries' rearrangement of the propionates of 4-chlorophenol and 4-chloro-3-methylphenol.

This method bids fair to be a general method for the synthesis of 3:4-dialkyl coumarin derivatives, which cannot be synthesised by methods known at present. The yields of the intermediate products and of the coumarins are highly satisfactory. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methoxy-5-chlorophenylethyl ketone was obtained from 2-propionyl-4-chlorophenol (Wittig, *Annalen*, 1925, 446, 186) with methyl iodide in alcoholic sodium ethoxide. It distils at 135-40°/6 mm. as a thick colourless oil, which solidifies on long standing, m.p. 41-42°. (Found: Cl, 17.64. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 17.88 per cent).

Ethyl α -Methyl- β -ethyl- β -hydroxy- β -(2-methoxy-5-chloro)-phenylpropionate.—A mixture of 2-methoxy-5-chlorophenylethyl ketone (7 g.), freshly distilled ethyl α -bromopropionate (7 g.), zinc wool (3 g.) and benzene (20 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours, when the zinc dissolved. The solution was then poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer separated, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and then with water and dried. On removing benzene it was collected at 155-60°/7 mm. as a thick yellow oil, yield 6.5 g. On standing the oil partly solidified and the solid was collected and crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m.p. 71°. (Found: Cl, 11.79. $C_{14}H_{21}O_4$ Cl requires Cl, 11.8 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methoxy-5-chloro- α -methyl- β -ethylcinnamate.—The product of condensation obtained above (5 g.) was converted into the unsaturated ester with thionyl chloride (2 g.) in the presence of pyridine (3 g.) in dry ethereal solution (100 c.c.). The ethereal layer after decomposing excess of thionyl chloride with ice was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, with alkali and then with water. On removing ether the product was distilled at 163°/6 mm. as a colourless oil which did not solidify on standing, yield quantitative.

3-Methyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin was obtained from the above unsaturated ester (1 g.) by heating with hydriodic acid (d 1.7, 5 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 140–50° for 2 hours. The oil obtained on pouring the mixture into water was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed repeatedly with dilute soda solution and finally with water. On removing ether the coumarin was obtained as colourless needles, which were recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 94°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : Cl, 15.77. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.95 per cent). It dissolves in warm alkali and is obtained unchanged on acidification. The ring-closure may also be effected with good yield by keeping overnight the unsaturated ester with a few c.c. of sulphuric acid (d 1.84).

Formation of 3:7-Dimethyl-4-ethyl-6-chlorocoumarin from 2-Methoxy-4-methyl-5-chlorophenylethyl ketone and Ethyl α -bromopropionate.—2-Methoxy-5-chloro-4-methylphenylethyl ketone, prepared from 2-propionyl-4-chloro-5-methylphenol (Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 84) with methyl iodide in alcoholic sodium ethoxide was crystallised from alcohol as colourless plates, m.p. 74°. (Found : Cl, 16.9. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 16.7 per cent).

The ketone (8 g.) and ethyl α -bromopropionate (8 g.) were condensed as above using zinc wool (4 g.) in dry benzene solution and the product (8 g. b.p. 170°/5 mm.) was converted into the unsaturated ester (b.p. 165°/5 mm.) with thionyl chloride in the presence of pyridine, yield quantitative. The unsaturated ester (2 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 140–45° for 2 hours with hydriodic acid (d 1.7, 6 c.c.). The solid separating on pouring the solution into water was crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m.p. 121°, yield 1.5 g. It dissolves in warm alkali to a yellow solution and is recovered on acidification. (Found : Cl, 14.78. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.01 per cent).